

1 **Evaluation of the precision and accuracy of models of enteric methane**
2 **emissions from ruminants using Bayesian inference**

3 P. Blondiaux ^a, E.H. Cabezas-Garcia ^{b,1}, T. Senga Kiessé ^c, R. Muñoz-Tamayo ^a,
4 K.F. Reed ^{b,2}, M. Eugène ^d

5

6 *^a Université Paris-Saclay, INRAE, AgroParisTech, UMR Modélisation Systémique*
7 *Appliquée aux Ruminants, 91120, Palaiseau, France*

8 *^b Department of Animal Science, Cornell University, Ithaca, NY, United States*

9 *^c INRAE, UMR SAS, Institut Agro, 35000 Rennes, France*

10 *^d Université Clermont Auvergne, INRAE, VetAgro Sup, UMR Herbivores, F-63122*
11 *Saint-Genes-Champanelle, France*

12

13 *¹ Present address: International Livestock Research Institute (ILRI), PO Box 30709,*
14 *Nairobi 00100, Kenya*

15 *² Present address: USDA-Agricultural Research Service US Dairy Forage Research*
16 *Center, Madison, WI 53706*

17

18 Corresponding author: Maguy Eugène. Email: maguy.eugene@inrae.fr

19 **Abstract**

20 Reducing enteric methane (CH₄) emissions from dairy cattle is essential to limit
21 global warming to the target of 1.5° C increase. Empirical models taken from the
22 literature are used to assess the impact of CH₄ mitigation strategies. Numerous
23 models developed are usually compared by quantifying the prediction error.

24 However, the uncertainty evaluation of CH₄ predictions reliability is rarely addressed.

25 This work fills this gap by comparing the predictive accuracy and precision of ten total
26 enteric CH₄ production models, incorporating uncertainty using Bayesian inference.
27 We assumed that integrating the uncertainty in model comparison can be useful to
28 select models suited for specific conditions. To assess the accuracy and precision of
29 models, three analyses were conducted: A1) Assessment of the probability of models
30 to predict within target areas representative of several accuracy levels around the
31 CH₄ observed, A2) Assessment of the relationship between bias and standard
32 deviation and A3) Assessment of the probability of models to predict lipid (EE)-level
33 based dietary scenarios. These analyses were conducted using two restricted
34 datasets RD1 (107 records) and RD2 (215 records), in particular RD2 explored a
35 larger diversity of dietary treatments than RD1. Results indicated that a model
36 associating dry matter intake (DMI), EE and neutral detergent fiber (NDF) digestibility
37 was the most recommendable, as it was among the most accurate models in A1 and
38 showed the best trade-off between accuracy and precision in A2, for both RD1 and
39 RD2. Moreover, using gross energy intake alone highlighted a higher accuracy than
40 using DMI alone in A1 and A2, with RD2. Including dietary composition variables
41 (NDF and/or EE) in addition to DMI did not always improve accuracy, which was the
42 case with RD1 but not with RD2. Milk yield (MY) alone could be an alternative to
43 DMI, as A1 highlighted a higher accuracy at 8% around the CH₄ observed. Also, the
44 most complex model had the highest accuracy in A1 and A2, raising question about
45 the trade-off between accuracy and complexity. Finally, A3 indicated that model
46 predictive ability was different depending on the EE-level of the diet. Using DMI alone
47 better predicted the low EE-level scenario, while MY alone better predicted medium
48 and high EE scenarios, despite large over- and underestimation of observed CH₄,
49 respectively. The probabilistic framework presented was relevant to provide

50 recommendations on model selection. Also, extending the A3 approach to reference
51 diets (INRAE, USDA, FAO) could benefit future work.

52 **Keywords:** Bayesian inference, Dairy cattle, Methane emission, Model evaluation,
53 Uncertainty analysis

54 **Implications**

55 In the effort to reduce enteric methane emissions from cattle and mitigate climate
56 change, numerous models are developed to assess the efficiency of mitigation
57 strategies. The challenge for modelers is to use the model that will provide the most
58 reliable methane predictions. In this perspective, our study evaluates the accuracy
59 and precision of ten models of enteric methane production widely used by modelers,
60 incorporating uncertainty using Bayesian inference. The best performing model used
61 dry matter intake, dietary lipid content and digestibility of dietary fiber content. The
62 probabilistic approach developed can be used to recommend models under specific
63 conditions.

64 **Highlights**

- 65 • The uncertainty of methane predictions of models needs to be characterized.
- 66 • Ten models using animal and diet characteristics were compared.
- 67 • A model with dry matter intake, lipid content and fiber digestibility was
68 accurate.
- 69 • Model performance was different depending on the dietary strategy studied.
- 70 • The framework developed in this work can be used to recommend models.

71 **Introduction**

72 Dairy cattle contribute significantly to global warming by emitting methane (CH₄)
73 through the feed digestion which takes place in the rumen. Enteric CH₄ produced
74 from the rumen fermentation from all livestock accounts for 20 - 25% of global CH₄
75 emissions from the livestock sector (Gerber et al., 2013). Methane is a potent
76 greenhouse gas with a global warming potential of 84 times that of carbon dioxide
77 (CO₂) over a 20-year period, but with a short atmospheric lifetime span of around
78 12.5 year (Myhre et al., 2013). Therefore, strong and rapid reductions of CH₄
79 emissions can have a positive effect on global warming at short time and are crucial
80 to limit global warming at 1.5° C above pre-industrials levels (IPCC, 2018). In addition
81 to the negative impact on the environment, enteric CH₄ emissions have also a
82 negative impact on feed efficiency. The dietary energy loss represented by the
83 production of CH₄ can vary from 2 to 12% of the gross energy intake (GEI) by the
84 animal, depending on the type of diet and the digestive efficiency of the animal
85 (Johnson and Johnson, 1995). Mitigating CH₄ emissions is a critical concern for the
86 dairy industry, as it can provide both environmental and economic benefits.

87 Optimizing the diet of dairy cattle is one of the strategies used to mitigate enteric CH₄
88 emissions (Beauchemin et al., 2022). Indeed, it is known that the animal's diet has a
89 significant effect on enteric CH₄ production, by affecting several mechanisms linked
90 to rumen fermentation. For instance, adding lipids to dairy cattle diets can reduce
91 enteric CH₄ production by up to 20% and improve feed efficiency (Beauchemin et al.,
92 2022, 2020; Hristov, 2024). However, mitigation efficiency depends on several
93 factors, such as the form, source and amount of lipids supplemented.

94 To assess the effectiveness of these dietary mitigation strategies and develop
95 national inventories of greenhouse gas, empirical mathematical models predicting
96 enteric CH₄ emissions are used because measurement techniques are expensive

97 and difficult to implement at large scale (Tedeschi et al., 2022). These models can be
98 general (Ramin and Huhtanen, 2013) or specific to ruminant categories (Nielsen et
99 al., 2013; Niu et al., 2018), dietary strategies (Feng et al., 2020; Arndt et al., 2022)
100 and/or regions (Charmley et al., 2016; IPCC 2019). Empirical models correspond to
101 regression equations using variables describing the animal characteristics, diet
102 composition and animal production. Among these variables, many studies identified
103 feed intake variables, represented mainly by dry matter intake (DMI) or GEI, as the
104 key factors explaining CH₄ emissions (Benaouda et al., 2019; Hristov et al., 2013; Niu
105 et al., 2018; Reynolds et al., 2011). However, including the effect of dietary and non-
106 dietary variables along with intake variables, can improve model predictions. Niu et
107 al. (2018), Moraes et al. (2014) and Ramin and Huhtanen (2013) found that adding
108 dietary and animal-specific variables with DMI or GEI improved model prediction
109 performance, even if this improvement is small.

110 To provide reliable recommendations to reduce enteric CH₄ production to countries
111 and industry, several works compared the predictive performance of models with
112 different level of complexity using intercontinental databases (Benaouda et al. (2019),
113 Niu et al. (2018) and Appuhamy et al. (2016)). Evaluation criteria included the root
114 mean square prediction error (RMSPE) and the concordance correlation coefficient
115 (CCC).

116 However, assessing model performance only by classical statistic metrics (RMSE,
117 CCC) might be limited since such an approach do not take into account the
118 uncertainty associated with the model prediction. Empirical models are subjected to
119 uncertainties because measurements of CH₄ and explanatory variables are not
120 perfect, system characteristics can vary, and time and space scale changes in
121 variables used can occur (Hristov et al., 2018). These uncertainties impact the

122 reliability of model CH₄ predictions. Therefore, integrating the uncertainty into model
123 assessment is of relevance and can provide a useful information to compare and
124 recommend models. However, to our knowledge there is no assessment of enteric
125 methane prediction model performance that quantifies model uncertainty and
126 accuracy available in the literature. Comparing the predictive performance of
127 empirical models with evaluation criteria that assesses model prediction accuracy
128 and precision provides a better understanding of model performance. These
129 measures can be useful to help select a model according to a precision level set by
130 the user. Accuracy measures how close a prediction is to its observation, whereas
131 precision measures how close the predictions of a same observation are to each
132 other. Bayesian inference is very useful to study both measures as it explicitly
133 quantifies uncertainty and represents the prediction of an observation as a probability
134 distribution function (PDF).

135 The use of Bayesian techniques is increasing in empirical models of enteric CH₄
136 emissions, allowing to quantify and incorporate uncertainty into models and to
137 improve prediction accuracy. Moraes et al. (2014) used a Bayesian model selection
138 procedure to select explanatory variables best predicting enteric CH₄ emissions.
139 Zheng et al. (2017) proposed a Bayesian network to model the interactions between
140 cow breed, energy corrected milk (ECM) yield, forage proportion in the diet and CH₄
141 yield (CH₄/DMI). This technique has been also used for dynamic models, where
142 Reed et al. (2016) and van Lingen et al. (2019) improved the calibration of
143 mechanistic models by integrating the uncertainty using Bayesian approaches.
144 However, to our knowledge Bayesian linear regression has not yet been applied to
145 compare extant models of enteric CH₄ production.

146 Our aim in this work is to assess and compare the precision and accuracy of several
147 existing empirical models of total enteric CH₄ production (g/d) of dairy cattle by
148 developing Bayesian linear regression models that account for uncertainty.

149 **Material and methods**

150 We used a published global database of enteric CH₄ production in dairy cows (de
151 Ondarza et al., 2023) and a list reporting several empirical models of the literature
152 (Blondiaux, 2024) to develop ten Bayesian linear regression models using different
153 variable categories and compare their accuracy and precision (Fig. 1).

154

Fig. 1. Illustration of the definition of accuracy and precision.

155

156 Models developed in the present study use variables previously selected in literature
157 dairy cattle models from Niu et al. (2018) and Marumo et al. (2023), which were
158 developed from intercontinental databases.

159 In the literature, three units of CH₄ emissions (production in g/d, yield in g/kg of DMI
160 and intensity in g/kg of milk yield (MY) or ECM) are usually considered, leading to

161 different interpretations of model predictions. In this study, we only focus on CH₄
 162 production (g/d) because it is most widely used in the field.

163 Finally, the general approach developed in our work is summarized in Fig. 2.

164

Fig. 2. Summary of the approach developed in our study.

165

166 ***Database of mitigation experiments of enteric methane emission from dairy***
 167 ***cattle***

168 A database of 797 CH₄ mitigation experiments of dairy cows from de Ondarza et al.
 169 (2023) was used to develop the Bayesian linear regressions. One observation of the
 170 database corresponded to the mean of one group of animals following the same
 171 treatment. Throughout the manuscript, the word record will refer to one observation
 172 of the database.

173 The referred database includes experiments conducted from 1963 to 2022 in 26
 174 countries, mainly in Europe (49%), North America (27%) and Oceania (12%).

175 Methane mitigation experiments in the data investigated include 12 dietary types

176 such as diet reformulation (43%), lipid supplementation in the diet (14%) and
177 inclusion of the feed additive 3-nitrooxypropanol in the diet (3%). Different CH₄
178 measurement methods were reported: the respiration chamber (54.5%), the
179 hexafluoride sulfur (SF₆) tracer technique (30.5%) and the GreenFeed system
180 (13.2%), respectively.

181 A total of 162 variables describing the experiment, animal characteristics, diet
182 composition, and animal production are collated in the database. The energy
183 corrected milk (ECM) was computed with the equation of Tyrrell and Reid (1965)
184 using milk fat (MF), milk protein (MP), and milk lactose (ML). The availability of these
185 variables was very heterogenous among categories.

186 ***Bayesian inference***

187 The Bayesian framework assumes that we have an initial knowledge on the variable
188 of interest. This initial knowledge can come from several sources of information, such
189 as expert knowledge or reliable data, and is represented by a PDF called prior
190 distribution. Using the Bayes formula, the prior distribution is updated with the data,
191 computing the posterior distribution:

$$192 \quad \mathbf{p}(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x}|\boldsymbol{\theta}) \cdot \mathbf{p}(\boldsymbol{\theta})}{\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x})} \quad (1)$$

193 With \mathbf{x} the variable of interest and $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ the parameters. $\mathbf{p}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ is the prior distribution
194 representing the initial knowledge of $\boldsymbol{\theta}$, $\mathbf{p}(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\mathbf{x})$ is the posterior distribution
195 representing the initial knowledge of $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ updated with the data \mathbf{x} , $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x}|\boldsymbol{\theta})$ is the
196 likelihood of the data \mathbf{x} given $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ and $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x})$ is the marginal likelihood.

197 The Bayesian linear regression transfers the linear regression to the probabilistic
198 framework and is described as follows:

$$199 \quad \mathbf{y} \sim \mathbf{N}(\mu = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot x_1 + \beta_2 \cdot x_2 + \dots + \beta_n \cdot x_n, \sigma = \varepsilon) \quad (2)$$

200 With y the dependent variable, x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n the explanatory variables, $\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_n$
201 the parameters of the linear expression. y is represented by a Gaussian distribution
202 of mean μ , corresponding to the linear expression studied, and of standard deviation
203 (SD) σ , corresponding to the residuals of the linear expression studied ε .
204 Basically, the Bayesian linear regression is performed in three steps: 1) set the prior
205 distributions over model parameters ($\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_n$ and ε), 2) estimate the posterior
206 distributions over model parameters using a Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC)
207 algorithm, and 3) compute the model prediction \hat{y} using the posterior distributions
208 previously estimated. The resulting \hat{y} is a PDF that can be used to describe and
209 quantify the uncertainty of model prediction. This representation of model prediction
210 is used to assess its accuracy and precision as it is detailed later.

211 ***Bayesian models of enteric methane production developed***

212 *Parameters of the Bayesian inference used*

213 We developed ten Bayesian linear regression models using the PyMC library in
214 Python (Abril-Pla et al., 2023). The posterior distributions were estimated using the
215 Hamiltonian Monte Carlo algorithm NUTS sampler (Hoffman and Gelman, 2014). We
216 ran four chains, drew 1000 posterior samples for each parameter and used 500 or
217 1000 samples for chains tuning. For each Bayesian model developed, evaluation of
218 the MCMC algorithm was performed by checking the samples of the four Markov
219 chains for each model parameter. The goodness of fit of the models was also
220 assessed by computing posterior predictive samples of CH_4 using the posterior
221 distributions estimated over model parameters.

222 *Selection of the variables*

223 The variables used in our models are displayed Table 1. They were selected as
 224 presented in empirical equations developed by Niu et al. (2018) and Marumo et al.
 225 (2023).

226 **Table 1**

227 Variables used in the Bayesian model developed

Model n°	Variables used	Reference
[1]	GEI	Niu et al. (2018)
[2]	DMI	Niu et al. (2018)
[3]	DMI + NDF	Niu et al. (2018)
[4]	DMI + EE	Niu et al. (2018)
[5]	DMI + EE + NDF	Niu et al. (2018)
[6]	EE + NDF	Niu et al. (2018)
[7]	MY	Niu et al. (2018)
[8]	ECM	Niu et al. (2018)
[9]	DMI + EE + NDF + MF + BW	Niu et al. (2018)
[10]	DMI + EE + NDFD	Marumo et al. (2023)

228 GEI = gross energy intake (MJ/d), DMI = dry matter intake (kg/d), NDF = neutral detergent fibre content (% of dry matter), EE =
 229 ether extract content (% of dry matter), MY = milk yield (kg/d), ECM = energy corrected milk (kg/d), MF = milk fat (%), BW =
 230 animal body weight (kg), NDFD = neutral detergent fibre digestibility (%).

231 Niu et al., (2018) aimed at developing intercontinental and region-specific (Europe
 232 and United States) models of CH₄ production, yield and intensity of dairy cattle. The
 233 authors used a sequential approach, developing models with an increasing level of
 234 complexity by progressively adding the different variable categories (animal

235 characteristics, intake, diet composition, and milk production and composition). The
236 variables selected for our models were from the intercontinental CH₄ production
237 models table. All the equation categories were retained, except those using ECM
238 with MP and MF (Table 1, models [1] to [9]). For each category, these variables were
239 selected in Niu et al. (2018) as they provided the best performance according to the
240 Bayesian information criterion, and the absence of multicollinearity was also
241 assessed.

242 In addition to Niu et al. (2018) models, a model using neutral detergent fibre (NDF, %
243 of dry matter (DM)) digestibility (NDFD, %) (Table 1, model [10]) was developed
244 following Marumo et al. (2023) to integrate dietary fiber digestibility variable in our
245 model comparison.

246 *Model development*

247 The precision and accuracy of the fitted Bayesian models were compared. The
248 accuracy was estimated by assessing the probability of CH₄ predictions to be in a
249 targeted area around the CH₄ observed. While, the precision was estimated by
250 assessing the standard deviation (SD) of CH₄ posterior predictive distribution. First, a
251 comparison including all the models (Table 1, models [1] to [10]) was performed
252 using a restricted dataset (RD) composed of animal characteristics, intake, diet
253 composition, diet digestibility, and milk production and composition variables. All
254 records associated with at least one missing value for one of the variables
255 considered were removed from the original database of de Ondarza et al. (2023)
256 (RD1, 107 records). Second, the seven models using intake, diet composition, and
257 digestibility variables (Table 1, models [1] to [6] and model [10]), were compared
258 using a restricted dataset including only these variables (RD2, 215 records) to
259 increase the number of data (de Ondarza et al., 2023). The RD1 was composed of

260 studies from Europe and North America, representing 81% and 15% of the records,
261 respectively. Dataset RD2 was also mainly composed of European studies (62%)
262 and North american studies (30%). Regarding the treatment types, RD1 and RD2
263 reported mainly diet reformulation (31 and 39%, respectively), lipid supplementation
264 (25 and 19%, respectively) and control (19 and 19%, respectively). The main CH₄
265 measurement technique used in both RD1 and RD2 was the respiration chamber
266 (with 73 and 66% of the records, respectively).
267 Finally, both datasets were split into training and testing datasets. The training
268 datasets corresponded to 75 (70%) and 172 (80%) records randomly selected from
269 RD1 and RD2, respectively. The remaining records constituted the test datasets of
270 both RD1 and RD2, representing 32 and 43 records for RD1 and RD2, respectively.

271 ***Development of prior distributions for explanatory variable parameter***
272 ***estimates***

273 A list of 64 extant empirical models of enteric CH₄ production based on previous work
274 (Marumo et al., 2023; Benaouda et al., 2019; Appuhamy et al., 2016) from 17 studies
275 conducted from 1997 to 2019 was built to define the prior distributions of parameters
276 associated with the explanatory variables used in the 10 Bayesian models developed
277 (Table 1). This list summarizes the initial knowledge of regression coefficient
278 estimates and their variability based on the lower and upper bounds of the
279 confidence intervals for each estimate. Thus, the prior distributions summarize both
280 the central tendency and the uncertainty of the parameter estimates available in the
281 literature. The complete list of parameter prior distributions is available in Blondiaux
282 (2024). The model complexity (one or several explanatory variables used in the
283 model) and the number of records used for model development were also reported.

284 Main regions represented are Europe, North America, and Oceania. Other regions
 285 (South America, Asia and Africa) were only represented when intercontinental
 286 databases were used for model development, but this representation is usually very
 287 low. The models reported can be specific to a region/system (Charmley et al., 2016;
 288 Ellis et al., 2007; Nielsen et al., 2013) or not (Hristov et al., 2013b; Niu et al., 2018;
 289 Storlien et al., 2014), but they were not specific to a dietary treatment. Moreover, they
 290 can be developed with data corresponding to individual animals (Ellis et al., 2007) or
 291 to means of group of animals (Appuhamy et al., 2016). Dairy cattle data were always
 292 used for model development alone (Mills et al., 2003; Niu et al., 2018; Storlien et al.,
 293 2014) or in combination with beef cattle data (Charmley et al., 2016; Ellis et al., 2007;
 294 Ramin and Huhtanen, 2013). Models developed for all animal categories were only
 295 considered for those sourced from the IPCC (2019, 2006, 1997).

296 To be selected a model must: have a linear regression form and include variables
 297 from the set of explanatory variables displayed in Table 2.

298 **Table 2**

299 Set of explanatory variables used in the list reporting extant empirical models of
 300 enteric CH₄ production (g/d) (Blondiaux, 2024)

Variable category	Variables
animal characteristics	BW (kg)
intake	GEI (MJ/d), DMI (kg/d), FL (g/kg BW)
diet composition	CP (%DM), NDF (%DM), EE (%DM), FA (%DM), STA (%DM), ash (%DM)
digestibility	DMD (%), OMD (%), NDFD (%), CPD (%)

milk production and
composition

MY (kg/d), ECM (kg/d), MF (%), MP (%)

301 BW = animal body weight (kg), GEI = gross energy intake (MJ/d), DMI = dry matter intake (kg/d), FL = feeding level (g/kg of
302 body weight), CP = crude protein content (% of dry matter), NDF = neutral detergent fibre content (% of dry matter), EE = ether
303 extract content (% of dry matter), FA = fatty acid content (% of dry matter), STA = starch content (% of dry matter), ash (% of dry
304 matter), DMD = dry matter digestibility (%), OMD = organic matter digestibility (%), NDFD = neutral detergent fibre digestibility
305 (%), CPD = crude protein digestibility (%), MY = milk yield (kg/d), ECM = energy corrected milk (kg/d), MF = milk fat (%), MP =
306 milk protein (%).

307 Variable units were standardized when different from those considered in our list.

308 Conversions were performed when it was possible, otherwise the model was

309 removed. All the models reported were checked for the absence of multicollinearity in

310 the original studies, mainly by computing the variance inflation factor.

311 A PDF for each regression coefficient used in the 10 models listed in Table 1 were

312 fitted using the Python distfit library. For each regression coefficient, several

313 distributions (Normal, Beta, etc) were tested and the most appropriate form was

314 selected based on the residual sum of squares and the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test.

315 The PDFs selected for each regression coefficient are displayed in Table 3. In

316 addition, when the number of data available to fit the PDF was low, a half-normal

317 distribution was selected to model parameter variability. A half normal distribution

318 was also fitted for the residual error term, ϵ , based on expert knowledge. These

319 PDFs constituted the prior distributions for the parameters of the Bayesian models

320 developed in the next steps.

321 **Table 3**

322 Prior distributions over Bayesian model parameters fitted using the list of extant
 323 empirical models, except for ε pdf which was selected based on expert knowledge.

Parameters	Distribution	Location	Scale	Parameter 1	Parameter 2
β_0	Log-normal	-539	591	6.38	0.16
β_{BW}	Gamma	0.01	0.09	0.86	11.1
β_{GEI}	Beta	0.57	0.88	1.92	2.19
β_{DMI}	Beta	-1.12	32.9	6.73	4.53
β_{NDF}	Beta	0.01	5.12	0.96	1.73
β_{EE}	Half-normal	-0.35	8.30		
β_{NDFD}	Half-normal	1.5	2		
β_{MY}	Half-normal	9.99e-06	2.38		
β_{ECM}	Half-normal	3.30	2		
β_{MF}	Half-normal	4.36	16.2		
ε	Half-normal	0	120		

324 β_0 = intercept of the regression model, β_{BW} = regression coefficient of animal body weight, β_{GEI} = regression coefficient of
 325 gross energy intake, β_{DMI} = regression coefficient of dry matter intake, β_{NDF} = regression coefficient of neutral detergent
 326 fibre content, β_{EE} = regression coefficient of ether extract content, β_{NDFD} = regression coefficient of neutral detergent fibre
 327 digestibility, β_{MY} = regression coefficient of milk yield, β_{ECM} = regression coefficient of energy corrected milk, β_{MF} =
 328 regression coefficient of milk fat, ε = residuals of the regression model.

329 ***Analysis of Bayesian model developed***

330 *Evaluation of model accuracy*

331 The Bayesian inference framework was used to assess model accuracy by
332 computing the probability of models to predict in a targeted area set by considering a
333 range th_{acc} (%) around the true CH₄ observed, which was defined as follows:

334
$$[obs_i - th_{acc}, obs_i + th_{acc}] \quad (3)$$

335 With obs_i is the i th observed value and th_{acc} is the accuracy threshold. We varied
336 th_{acc} from 1 to 10% for the comparison including all the models with RD1 or from 1 to
337 20% for the comparison including only the empirical models using intake, diet
338 composition, and diet digestibility variables with RD2. This approach allows users to
339 set areas of several widths associated with several levels of accuracy around 1%, 10
340 or 20% of the true CH₄ observed. The ability of models to predict in these different
341 accuracy areas was assessed by computing the probability of their predictions to be
342 within the targeted area, as follows:

343
$$P_i(\mathbf{pred}_i \in [obs_i \pm th_{acc}]) = \frac{n_{\mathbf{pred}_i \in [obs_i \pm th_{acc}]}}{n} \quad (4)$$

344 With \mathbf{pred}_i is the i th predictive posterior sample, obs_i is the i th observed value and
345 th_{acc} is the accuracy threshold. $n_{\mathbf{pred}_i \in [obs_i \pm th_{acc}]}$ corresponds to the number of
346 values of the i th predictive posterior sample within the target area $[obs_i \pm th_{acc}]$.
347 Finally, n is the number of values constituting the posterior predictive sample which
348 was set to 1000.

349 These probabilities were computed for all the records of RD1 and RD2 test datasets.
350 The median values of 32 and 43 probabilities computed for RD1 and RD2,
351 respectively, were considered to assess the overall accuracy of models.

352 *Evaluation of the relationship between bias and standard deviation*

353 Model accuracy and precision was also studied by assessing the relationship
354 between bias and SD.
355 The bias of model predictions was computed by considering the average difference
356 between model predictive posterior samples and the CH₄ observed for all the records
357 of RD1 and RD2 test datasets. Moreover, the SD of the posterior predictive samples
358 was computed to assess model precision.
359 Similar to the evaluation of model accuracy, the median values of 32 and 43 biases
360 and SD computed for RD1 and RD2, respectively, were considered to assess the
361 overall bias and precision of models.

362 *Evaluation of the model accuracy using dietary scenarios*

363 We also investigated the ability of some models to predict 3 dietary scenarios
364 selected in RD1.
365 The 3 dietary scenarios were set by simulating lipid supplementation, where it was
366 defined by selecting records of the test dataset of RD1 associated with three levels of
367 dietary ether extract content (EE, % of DM) in the diet (Low=min EE, Medium=mean
368 EE and High=max EE). Lipid supplementation in the diet is well known to reduce CH₄
369 production (Arndt et al., 2022; Beauchemin et al., 2022; Benaouda et al., 2019).
370 Therefore, the aim was to investigate how the predictive ability of some models was
371 impacted by several EE-levels in a diet. The three dietary scenarios studied are
372 displayed in Table 4.

373 **Table 4**

374 Dietary scenarios studied

Dietary scenario	CH ₄ (g/d)	BW (kg)	GEI (MJ/d)	DMI (kg/d)	NDF (%DM)	EE (%DM)	NDFD (%)	MY (kg/d)	ECM (kg/d)	MF (%)
Three levels of lipid content (EE, %DM)										
Low	387	632	323	17.5	32.5	2.10	48.4	23.6	25.9	4.62
Medium	415	617	429	23.7	34.5	3.13	49.6	29.5	32.0	4.55
High	475	705	359	19.1	37.8	8.50	59.5	29.0	29.1	4.18

375 BW = animal body weight (kg), GEI = gross energy intake (MJ/d), DMI = dry matter intake (kg/d), NDF = neutral detergent fibre
376 content (% of dry matter), EE = ether extract content (% of dry matter), NDFD = neutral detergent fibre digestibility (%), MY =
377 milk yield (kg/d), ECM = energy corrected milk (kg/d), MF = milk fat (%).

378 The predictive ability of simple models (Table 1, models [2] and [7]) and complex
379 models (Table 1, models [9] and [10]) were assessed on the three dietary scenarios.
380 Moreover, these models were selected because, combined, they used all the variable
381 categories selected.
382 For each dietary scenario, the probability of model prediction to be below a given CH₄
383 threshold value was computed as follows:

$$384 \quad P_i(\mathbf{pred}_i \leq th_{CH_4}) = \frac{n_{\mathbf{pred}_i \leq th_{CH_4}}}{n} \quad (5)$$

385 With \mathbf{pred}_i is the *i*th predictive posterior sample and th_{CH_4} is the threshold of CH₄
386 ranging from 150 to 800 g/d with a step of 10 g/d. $n_{\mathbf{pred}_i \leq th_{CH_4}}$ corresponds to the
387 number of values of the *i*th predictive posterior sample equal or below th_{CH_4} . Finally,
388 $n = 1000$ is the number of values constituting the posterior predictive sample.

389 The computation of these probabilities supports analysis of the risk of exceeding a
390 CH₄ value considering a given diet which provides relevant information for selection
391 of models for assessment of specific diet conditions.

392 Similar to the first analysis, an accuracy area was considered around the true CH₄
 393 observed for each dietary scenario to investigate model accuracy. These areas were
 394 set by setting $th_{acc} = 8\%$.

395 Other dietary scenarios, based on DMI- and NDF-levels, were studied using test
 396 datasets of RD1 and RD2. They are available in the supplementary material
 397 (Blondiaux, 2024).

398 Finally, following Open Science practices (Muñoz-Tamayo et al., 2022), the script
 399 was made available (Blondiaux, 2024).

400 **Results**

401 ***Description of datasets used for model development***

402 Summary statistics of RD1 and RD2 are available in Table 5.

403 **Table 5**

404 Summary statistics of the restricted datasets 1 (composed of animal characteristics,
 405 intake, diet composition, diet digestibility, and milk production and composition
 406 variables) and 2 (composed of intake, diet composition and digestibility variables).

	Restricted dataset 1				Restricted dataset 2			
Variables	Mean	Min	Max	SD	Mean	Min	Max	SD
	Training dataset (n=75)				Training dataset (n=172)			
CH ₄ (g/d)	415	149	547	71.9	371	90.4	614	108
BW (kg)	620	463	712	63.1				
GEI (MJ/d)	367	258	513	63.7	343	91.8	513	87.4
DMI (kg/d)	19.6	14.4	27.9	3.45	18.6	4.46	28.1	4.63

NDF	34.9	27.1			35.8	25.6	72.2	6.16
(%DM)			49.2	4.90				
EE (%DM)	4.17	1.65	8.53	1.81	3.91	1.65	8.53	1.57
NDFD (%)	61.6	38.1	86.5	9.18	55.8	23.7	86.5	10.5
MY (kg/d)	26.4	15.8	41.5	5.54				
ECM (kg/d)	27.8	16.3	42.8	5.12				
MF (%)	4.38	3.23	6.90	0.53				
	Test dataset (n = 32)				Test dataset (n = 43)			
CH ₄ (g/d)	426	284	614	80.2	375	77.6	547	104
BW (kg)	625	471	711	67.0				
GEI (MJ/d)	384	302	505	63.7	352	87.7	521	99.1
DMI (kg/d)	20.7	16.1	28.1	3.60	19.1	4.33	27.9	5.37
NDF	33.9	27.1			35.8	25.6	73.1	8.52
(%DM)			41.5	3.90				
EE (%DM)	3.68	2.10	8.50	1.62	4.03	2.08	8.51	1.65
NDFD (%)	55.4	36.5	69.6	8.16	54.5	29.1	79.5	10.7
MY (kg/d)	28.4	18.5	37.9	5.86				
ECM (kg/d)	29.6	20.0	40.7	4.93				
MF (%)	4.31	3.72	6.55	0.59				

407 BW = animal body weight (kg), GEI = gross energy intake (MJ/d), DMI = dry matter intake (kg/d), NDF = neutral detergent fibre

408 content (% of dry matter), EE = ether extract content (% of dry matter), NDFD = neutral detergent fibre digestibility (%), MY =

409 milk yield (kg/d), ECM = energy corrected milk (kg/d), MF = milk fat (%).

410 The training datasets of RD1 (n = 75) and RD2 (n = 172) showed different range of

411 variation for CH₄, DMI and GEI values. The removal of dry cows or observations not

412 reporting body weight (BW), MY, ECM and MF in RD1 led to the elimination of low

413 CH₄ producer records, with CH₄ production ranging from 149 to 547 g/d for RD1
414 against 90.4 to 614 g/d for RD2. This was also the case of DMI and GEI with a
415 minimum value of 14.4 kg/d and 258 MJ/d for RD1 against 4.46 g/d and 91.8 MJ/d for
416 RD2. Therefore, the variability explored was much wider in RD2 than in RD1, with SD
417 of 71.9 g/d and 3.45 kg/d for RD1 against 108 g/d and 4.63 kg/d for RD2, for CH₄ and
418 DMI, respectively. This suggests that RD1 and RD2 were not representative of the
419 same type of animals. RD1 was only composed of high CH₄ producer animal records,
420 while RD2 was composed of low and high CH₄ producer animal records.
421 For the other variables, RD2 explores higher and lower NDF and NDFD values than
422 RD1, respectively. Whereas, dietary EE was similar between both training datasets.
423 The comparison of training and test datasets for RD1 (n = 32) and RD2 (n = 43)
424 indicated that the variability explored by the test datasets was representative of that
425 in the training datasets. However, the test dataset of RD1 showed slightly higher
426 values for CH₄ and DMI than the training dataset.

427 ***Analysis of Bayesian model developed***

428 *Evaluation of model accuracy*

429 The approach conducted to assess model accuracy is described in Fig. 3. We
430 computed the probability of model prediction to be within an increasingly target area
431 defined by the threshold th_{acc} . The figure describes the approach for one record of
432 the test dataset of RD1.

433

Fig. 3. Evaluation of model accuracy by computing the probability of models to predict in a target area around the true methane record. This figure is an illustration for one test record.

434

435 Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 display the median probabilities of model predictions to be within an
 436 accuracy area around the true CH_4 observed according to the threshold used, for the
 437 32 and 43 records of test datasets of RD1 and RD2. One probability was computed
 438 for each of the 32 or 43 test records of RD1 and RD2, respectively. Then, the median
 439 of the 32 (or 43) probabilities calculated is displayed at each threshold th_{acc} to
 440 analyze the overall model accuracy.

441 *Models using animal characteristics, intake, diet composition, diet digestibility, and*
 442 *milk production and composition variables*

443 The results presented in Fig. 4 indicated that all the models were unable to predict in
 444 an area of 5% around each 32 values of CH₄ observed with RD1. From $th_{acc} = 1$ to
 445 5%, the maximum median of the probabilities to predict within these accuracy areas
 446 was 0.13, which indicates that half of the records had a maximum probability of 0.13
 447 that their predictions were inside the area for all the models. Only model [9] showed a
 448 median probability higher than 0.10, while other models were lower than 0.05,
 449 respectively.

450

Fig. 4. Median probability of model predictions developed with the restricted dataset 1 (composed of animal characteristics, intake, diet composition, digestibility and milk production and composition variables) to be within an accuracy area around the methane observed according to the threshold used to define this accuracy area (th_{acc}).

451

452 At $th_{acc} = 6\%$, these median probabilities increased but they were still lower than
 453 0.40 for all the models. Whereas, at $th_{acc} = 7\%$ the median probabilities of models
 454 [2], [3], [4], [5], [7], [9] and [10] increased significantly from 0.04, 0.09, 0.12, 0.11,

455 0.07, 0.38 and 0.19 to 0.18, 0.40, 0.46, 0.29, 0.28, 0.69 and 0.42, respectively.

456 Finally, almost all the models (except model [6]) were associated with high
457 probabilities to predict in an area of 10% around the CH₄ observed with a median
458 probability higher than 0.80, which indicated that half of the records had a probability
459 higher than 0.80 that their predictions were inside the area for these models.

460 Furthermore, from $th_{acc} = 5$ to 10% model [9] had the highest probability to predict
461 within the accuracy area around the CH₄ observed defined by these thresholds with,
462 for instance, a median probability to predict at 7% around the CH₄ observed of 0.69,
463 while it was lower than 0.50 for the other models.

464 The other models associated with the highest probabilities to predict in the referred
465 accuracy areas were: [3], [4] and [10]. Model [10] had the second highest median
466 probability at $th_{acc} = 6\%$, with a value of 0.19 against 0.09 and 0.12 for models [3]
467 and [4], respectively, before being slightly overtaken by models [3] and [4] when
468 considering higher accuracy threshold.

469 Model [5] which combined the two dietary composition variables with DMI showed a
470 similar accuracy to models [3] and [4], which used each of these dietary composition
471 variables alone with DMI, at $th_{acc} = 6\%$. Then, when increasing th_{acc} , models [3] and
472 [4] had a higher accuracy.

473 Model [2], which used DMI alone, had a lower accuracy than models combining other
474 variable categories with DMI (models [3], [4], [5], [9] and [10]). These median
475 probabilities were of 0.17, 0.50 and 0.86 against minimum 0.29, 0.62 and 0.88 for the
476 other models using DMI, at $th_{acc} = 7, 8$ and 9%, respectively. However, model [2]
477 showed a largely higher accuracy than model [1], which used GEI and had a low
478 accuracy with a median probability lower than 0.50 at $th_{acc} = 9\%$.

479 Regarding the milk production variable used to predict CH₄ production, model [7],
480 which used MY, had a much higher accuracy than model [8], which used ECM, with a
481 median probability ranging from 0.28 to 0.98 for model [7] against 0.01 to 0.89 for
482 model [8], for th_{acc} ranging from 7 to 10%. Moreover, it showed also a higher
483 accuracy than model [2] at $th_{acc} = 7\%$, with a median probability of 0.28 against 0.18
484 for model [2].
485 Finally, model [6], which used only diet composition variables, had largely the lowest
486 accuracy with a median probability of 0.10 at $th_{acc} = 10\%$.

487 *Models using intake, diet composition, and diet digestibility variables*

488 The results presented in Fig. 5 highlighted that models developed with RD2, which
489 explored a larger variability of CH₄ values than RD1, were associated with a lower
490 accuracy than models developed with RD1. The maximum median probability at
491 $th_{acc} = 8\%$ around the CH₄ observed was of 0.40 against 0.91 for models developed
492 with RD1.

493

Fig. 5. Median probability of model predictions developed with the restricted dataset 2 (composed of intake, diet composition and digestibility variables) to be within an accuracy area around the methane observed according to the threshold used to define this accuracy area (th_{acc}).

494

495 This maximum was reached for model [10], which was already in the pool of the most
 496 accurate models in Fig. 4. This model had the highest accuracy throughout the
 497 threshold considered, with a median probability of 0.85 to predict at 9% around the
 498 CH_4 observed, while it was lower than 0.53 for the other models.

499 Model [1] had the second highest accuracy, with a median probability of 0.86 to
 500 predict at 10% around the CH_4 observed. This result was different from Fig. 4, where
 501 model [1] was associated with one of the lowest performances.

502 At $th_{acc} = 9\%$, model [3] had the third highest accuracy with a median probability of
 503 0.27. Whereas, at $th_{acc} = 10\%$ models [2], which used DMI alone, and [5], which
 504 used DMI and the two diet composition variables, surpassed it with median
 505 probabilities of 0.59 and 0.57, respectively. Finally, from $th_{acc} = 11$ to 13%, it was
 506 models [2] and [3] which had the third highest accuracy with median probabilities

507 ranging from 0.84 to 1.0 and 0.85 to 1.0, respectively. In the same time, model [5]
 508 had not increased significantly, reaching a median probability of 1.0 at $th_{acc} = 15\%$.
 509 Model [4], which had a high accuracy in Fig. 4, showed the lowest accuracy among
 510 models using intake variables. These median probabilities to predict within an
 511 accuracy area at $th_{acc} = 10, 11, 12$ and 13% around the CH_4 observed were of 0.29,
 512 0.61, 0.67 and 0.84, respectively.

513 Similar to Fig. 4, model [6] had largely the lowest accuracy with a median probability
 514 to predict within an accuracy area below $th_{acc} = 18\%$ around the CH_4 observed of
 515 less than 0.10.

516 *Evaluation of the relationship between bias and standard deviation*

517 Table 6 displays the bias and SD of model predictions developed with RD1 and RD2,
 518 respectively. For each model, bias and SD were computed for the 32 and 43 records
 519 of test datasets of RD1 and RD2, respectively, and the medians were displayed to
 520 analyze the overall model accuracy and precision.

521 **Table 6**

522 Median bias and standard deviation (SD) of model predictions developed with the
 523 restricted datasets 1 (composed of animal characteristics, intake, diet composition,
 524 diet digestibility, and milk production and composition variables) and 2 (composed of
 525 intake, diet composition, and diet digestibility variables). The models were ranked in
 526 ascending order of bias.

Model	Bias (g CH_4/d)	SD (g CH_4/d)
Restricted dataset 1		
DMI + EE + NDF (5)	28.5	4.44

DMI + EE + NDFD (10)	29.7	3.97
DMI + EE + NDF + MF + BW (9)	30.0	4.55
DMI + EE (4)	30.4	4.08
MY (7)	30.5	4.04
DMI (2)	30.9	3.43
DMI + NDF (3)	31.6	3.78
GEI (1)	35.4	3.26
ECM (8)	36.6	3.50
EE + NDF (6)	55.8	5.10

Restricted dataset 2

DMI + EE + NDFD (10)	27.7	3.48
DMI + EE (4)	33.9	3.17
GEI (1)	34.2	2.47
DMI (2)	35.1	2.77
DMI + EE + NDF (5)	35.3	3.58
DMI + NDF (3)	35.5	3.16
EE + NDF (6)	69.0	4.61

527 GEI = gross energy intake (MJ/d), DMI = dry matter intake (kg/d), NDF = neutral detergent fibre content (% of dry matter), EE =
528 ether extract content (% of dry matter), MY = milk yield (kg/d), ECM = energy corrected milk (kg/d), MF = milk fat (%), BW =
529 animal body weight (kg), NDFD = neutral detergent fibre digestibility (%).

530 *Models using animal characteristics, intake, diet composition, diet digestibility and*

531 *milk production and composition variables*

532 The evaluation conducted with RD1 highlighted that models adding animal

533 characteristics, diet composition, diet digestibility, and milk composition variables to

534 DMI (models [4], [5], [9] and [10]) decreased the bias but increased SD of model [2]
535 (bias = 30.9 g/d, SD = 3.43 g/d), except for model [3] which was associated with a
536 larger bias (= 31.6 g/d) than model [2]. However, model [3] showed a lower SD (=
537 3.78 g/d) than other models using DMI with additional variables (> 3.97 g/d).
538 Models [5] and [10], which both included EE, and NDF for one and NDFD for the
539 other, were associated with the lowest biases (28.5 and 29.7 g/d, respectively), while
540 other models showed a bias higher than 30 g/d. Model [10] showed a lower SD than
541 model 5 (SD = 3.97 vs. 4.44 g/d).
542 Furthermore, all the models associated with the lowest biases included both EE and
543 DMI. Model [9], which was the most complex model, and model [4], which used EE
544 alone with DMI, displayed the third and fourth lowest biases, respectively. However,
545 these models were associated with the highest SD, when comparing with other
546 models using intake or milk production variables. Their SD were of 4.55 and 4.08,
547 respectively.
548 Model [7], which used only MY, provided a slightly lowest bias than model [2] (30.5
549 vs 30.9 g/d) but was associated with a larger SD (4.04 vs 3.43 g/d). When comparing
550 model [7] with the other model using milk production variable (model [8]), it showed a
551 better performance in terms of bias (30.5 vs 36.6 g/d) and SD (4.04 vs 3.50 g/d).
552 Model [1], which was already associated with a low performance in Fig. 4, showed
553 the third highest bias (= 35.4 g/d), largely higher than other models using intake
554 variables and model [7]. However, it showed the lowest SD (= 3.26 g/d).
555 Finally, model [6], which only used diet composition variables, was largely associated
556 with the highest bias (= 55.8 g/d) and SD (= 5.10 g/d).

557 *Models using intake, diet composition, and diet digestibility variables*

558 When a larger variability of animals was explored in RD2, model [10] had the lowest
559 bias (= 27.7 g/d), while other models had a bias higher than 30 g/d. However, its SD
560 was the second highest but it was the most complex model considered with model
561 [5].

562 Models [4] and [1] were then associated with lowest biases with closed values of 33.9
563 and 34.2 g/d. In addition, their SD were much lower than model [10] (3.17 and 2.47
564 g/d, respectively). This result was similar to the one obtained with RD1 for model [4]
565 but it was really different for model [1].

566 Models using NDF with DMI (models [3] and [5]) showed the highest biases for the
567 models using intake variables (= 35.3 and 35.5 g/d, respectively), with a high (model
568 [5]) and medium (model [3]) SD. Their bias was also slightly higher than model [2] (=
569 35.1 g/d). Model [5] also showed the highest SD (= 3.58 g/d), slightly higher than the
570 one of the other most complex models (model [10]). Whereas model [3] was
571 associated with the lowest SD (= 3.16 g/d) when not considering the two simple
572 models. A similar result was highlighted in the comparison with RD1.

573 Finally, similar to the model comparison on RD1, model [6] had the highest bias (=
574 69.0 g/d) and SD (= 4.61 g/d).

575 *Evaluation of model accuracy using dietary scenarios*

576 Fig. 6 displays the probability of predictions of models [2], [7], [9] and [10] developed
577 with RD1 to be below a CH₄ threshold value given a dietary scenario based on the
578 level of dietary EE in the diet.

579

Low lipid content level (EE = 2.10 %DM)

Medium lipid content level (EE = 3.13 %DM)

High lipid content level (EE = 8.50 %DM)

Fig. 6. Probability of model predictions developed with restricted dataset 1 (composed of animal characteristics, intake, diet composition, digestibility and milk production and composition variables) to be below a CH₄ threshold value (th_{CH_4}) for the three dietary scenarios based on level of lipid content (EE, % of dry matter) (Low: EE = 2.10 %DM, Medium: EE = 3.13 %DM and High: EE = 8.50 %DM).

581

582 The low EE-level scenario highlighted that model [2] provided the best performance
583 with a high probability of 0.67 to predict above 380 g/d and of 0.99 to predict below
584 390 g/d (CH₄ observed = 387 g/d). Other models were inside the accuracy area but
585 did not capture the CH₄ observed. Models [7] and [9] slightly overestimated the CH₄
586 observed with a probability of 0.05 and 0.02 to predict below 390 g/d. The range of
587 variation of their prediction was similar, ranging from 390 to 410 g/d, with a slightly
588 better performance for model [7], which was associated with a probability of 0.87 to
589 predict below 400 g/d against 0.61 for model [9]. Model [10] was associated with the
590 least satisfactory prediction, by underestimating the CH₄ observed. Its probability of
591 predicting below 370 g/d was of 0.99. However, its probability of predicting above
592 350 g/d, which was closed to the lower bound of the accuracy area (= 356 g/d), was
593 of 0.98.

594 The medium EE-level scenario highlighted that most of the models largely
595 overestimated the CH₄ observed (= 415 g/d), predicting below the accuracy area
596 except for model [7]. This model showed largely the most satisfactory performance
597 with a high probability of 0.90 to predict below 440 g/d. Therefore, this model
598 predicted inside the accuracy area, with an upper bound at 448 g/d. Among the other
599 models, model [10] showed the least worst performance, followed by models [2] and

600 [9], with low probabilities of 0.18, 0.005 and 0.01 to predict below 460, 470 and 480
601 g/d, respectively.

602 Finally, for the high EE-level scenario, all the models largely underestimated the CH₄
603 observed (= 475 g/d) and were outside the accuracy area, with a minimum probability
604 of 0.99 to predict below 440 g/d (lower bound of accuracy area = 437 g/d). Model [7]
605 provided largely the best satisfactory prediction with a high probability of 0.68 to
606 predict above 430 g/d and of 0.99 to predict below 440 g/d. It was followed by model
607 [2] with predictions ranging from 400 to 410 g/d. Models [9] and [10], which were the
608 most complex models, showed the lowest performances with a probability of 0.86
609 and 0.83 to predict below 390 g/d, respectively.

610 **Discussion**

611 ***A model associating dry matter intake with lipid content and neutral detergent*** 612 ***fiber digestibility is the best***

613 Based on our results, model [10], which used DMI, EE and NDFD, was the most
614 recommendable model. For both RD1 and RD2, it was selected among the most
615 accurate models, when assessing the probability to predict in a targeted area around
616 the CH₄ observed, and showed the best trade-off between accuracy and precision,
617 when assessing both the bias and SD. Moreover, this model was associated with a
618 reasonable complexity, involving only three explanatory variables. Our work confirms
619 the complementary information provided by these three variables (DMI, EE, NDFD)
620 to capture the variability of CH₄ production as previously reported. Indeed, the
621 important role of NDFD, assessing forage quality, in enteric CH₄ production in the
622 rumen was already highlighted in several studies (Brask et al., 2013; Knapp et al.,
623 2014; Warner et al., 2016).

624 Furthermore, model [10] revealed a higher accuracy than model [5], which used NDF
625 instead of NDFD, suggesting the better ability of NDFD to explain CH₄ production
626 compared to NDF. This is in agreement with several authors (Ramin and Huhtanen,
627 2013; Knapp et al., 2014; Appuhamy et al., 2016), who highlighted that in the rumen
628 the degradation of the fiber drives the total tract digestion and the rate of
629 fermentation in animals fed forage-based diets and, consequently, modulates
630 hydrogen and CH₄ emissions (Ungerfeld, 2020). Also, when assessed with RD2,
631 model [10] showed a largely higher accuracy than model [4], which associated DMI
632 with EE, confirming that NDFD contributes to add relevant information explaining CH₄
633 production variability. (Ramin and Huhtanen, 2013). However, NDFD is not easily
634 measurable in the field (Huhtanen and Vanhatalo, 1997). On the other hand, despite
635 the use of EE in model [10], the assessment of EE-based dietary scenarios revealed
636 that its predictive ability was negatively impacted by extreme levels (low or high) of
637 EE in the diet, with a large underestimation of the CH₄ observed. This highlights the
638 poor ability of this model to predict extreme levels of lipid supplementation and can
639 be explained by the insufficient level of information provided by DMI, EE and NDFD
640 for these extreme diets.

641 ***Gross energy intake is more accurate than dry matter intake to predict highly***
642 ***diverse diets***

643 The use of GEI as a single prediction factor (model [1]), which is the variable used by
644 the IPCC (IPCC, 2019, 2006, 1997) for the national inventories of greenhouse gases,
645 highlighted the highest accuracy with model [10] and a good trade-off between
646 accuracy and precision, when exploring a large diversity of diets in RD2. This result
647 is not in line with Ellis et al. (2010), which highlighted the limited capacity of GEI

648 alone to represent variation in CH₄ production due to dietary composition changes.
649 However, this is in agreement with several studies (Benaouda et al., 2019; Moraes et
650 al., 2014; Niu et al., 2018) which reported the good ability of GEI to predict CH₄
651 production in presence of a variety of diets.
652 The performance of model [1] was different when considering only high intake level
653 diets in RD1. Thus, in this case, model [1] was precise but not accurate, ranking
654 among the poorest models in terms of accuracy. This reveals the limitations of using
655 only GEI to predict CH₄ production when a low variability of diets was explored. Dry
656 matter intake appears as the most recommendable intake variables for this
657 subpopulation of high intake level diets.

658 ***Including dietary composition variables to dry matter intake does not***
659 ***necessarily improve model accuracy***

660 Adding diet composition variables to DMI (NDF in model [3], EE in model [4] and EE
661 and NDF in model [5]) improved the accuracy of using DMI alone (model [2]), when
662 exploring only high intake level diets in RD1. The result obtained with RD1 is in line
663 with previous studies (Benaouda et al., 2019; Moraes et al., 2014; Niu et al., 2018).
664 Moreover, Marumo et al. (2023) highlighted an improvement of model performance
665 for its two databases when increasing the complexity of the model using DMI by the
666 addition of diet composition variables. However, Appuhamy et al. (2016) suggested
667 that the low performance of models based on dietary composition was due to the
668 diversity of diet composition in European diets, but this was opposite to our results
669 (85% of European data). These results were not found for RD2, presumably because
670 of the larger variability of intake levels explored in this dataset.

671 The evaluation conducted with RD1 also indicated that EE was associated with a
672 slightly higher predictive accuracy than NDF. While, when exploring a wider range of
673 diets and fiber content in RD2, NDF showed a largely higher ability to predict close to
674 the CH₄ observed than EE. This last result was similar to Niu et al., (2018). Moreover,
675 Moe and Tyrrell (1979) and Nielsen et al. (2013) also highlighted NDF as the key diet
676 composition variable for predicting CH₄ production of dairy cows. The different results
677 between RD1 and RD2 can be explained by the high representation of lipid
678 supplementation treatment in RD1 and RD2 (25 vs 19% of the records, respectively).
679 For the precision, NDF showed a lower precision than EE in RD1, while their
680 precision were similar in RD2. This suggests that EE was more sensitive to the lack
681 of data than NDF, as the number of data available was more important for RD2
682 compares to RD1. Finally, the association of EE and NDF with DMI in model [5] did
683 not improve the probability of models [3] and [4] to predict close to the CH₄ observed.
684 Niu et al. (2018) highlighted a slightly better performance of model [5] compared to
685 model [4], but a slightly worse compared to model [3]. Also, model [5] was associated
686 with a high performance to predict Nordic dairy cow data in Nielsen et al., (2013).
687 To conclude, at a rather low targeted accuracy of 9% around the CH₄ observed,
688 model using NDF with DMI is the recommended equation among models using DMI
689 and diet composition variables. Whereas, when a lowest accuracy can be targeted,
690 adding diet composition variables to DMI do not improve the accuracy, and the use of
691 DMI alone is recommended. Moreover, this model showed a good performance at
692 predicting the low EE-level dietary scenario.

693 The main issue with DMI is its unavailability from commercial farms due to the
694 complexity of its measurement (Appuhamy et al., 2016; Blake et al., 2023; Delagarde
695 et al., 2011; Hristov et al., 2018). To try to solve this issue, Appuhamy et al. (2016)

696 redeveloped highly performant models including DMI using the estimated DMI and
697 revealed that satisfactory performances could be achieved using the estimated DMI
698 for North American data.

699 ***Milk yield can sometimes be an alternative to dry matter intake to predict***
700 ***methane***

701 The variables related to milk production are generally much more available in
702 practice than intake variables. Two milk production variables were considered alone
703 in our work: MY (model [7]) and ECM (model [8]). Our results indicated that model [7]
704 provided a much higher accuracy and precision than model [8]. Therefore, our
705 recommendation would be to use MY instead of ECM, when DMI or GEI is omitted
706 from the model to predict CH₄ production. Moreover, MY was more accurate than
707 DMI when targeted an accuracy of 8% around the CH₄ observed, and showed the
708 best ability to predict EE-based dietary scenarios. These results suggest the good
709 ability of MY to detect changes in diet composition, and highlight that MY could be an
710 alternative to DMI in some cases. However, these findings were not in agreement
711 with previous studies. Marumo et al. (2023) showed that models using MY or ECM
712 alone were associated with similar poor performances (RSR = 0.66 and 0.65,
713 respectively, vs 0.53 for the model using DMI alone). Moreover, in Niu et al. (2018)
714 the models using MY or ECM alone were also associated with higher RSR than
715 models using DMI or GEI alone when evaluated with intercontinental, European or
716 US data. Also, the model of Corré (2002) was never ranked in the top 10 models
717 when evaluated with North American, European and Oceanian data in Appuhamy et
718 al. (2016). Regarding the comparison between MY and ECM, Niu et al. (2018) found
719 that the model using ECM alone showed a better performance than the model using

720 MY alone for the intercontinental, European and US datasets. Furthermore, this
721 study revealed that using ECM with milk composition information was able to improve
722 the performance compared with the equation that used MY only.

723 ***Other model studied***

724 Similar to Niu et al. (2018) where it showed the lowest RSR when developed with
725 intercontinental data and evaluated with intercontinental, European and US data, the
726 most complex model studied involving intake, diet composition, milk composition and
727 BW variables (model [9]) showed the highest performance in our work with a high
728 probability to predict within a target area at 8% around the CH₄ observed. The
729 accuracy evaluation was not conducted specifically with European and US data in
730 our work due to the lack of data available. However, due to its high complexity, model
731 [9] showed a low precision. This raises the question of the trade-off between model
732 accuracy and complexity. In general, model complexity is positively correlated with
733 model accuracy (Moraes et al., 2014; Niu et al., 2018; Santiago-Juarez et al., 2016).
734 In our work, the most complex models were not necessarily associated with the
735 highest accuracy. In addition, complex models are limited by the lack of availability of
736 some variables difficult to measure in the field, leading to less data for model
737 development.
738 Finally, the model using only diet composition variables (model [6]) was associated
739 with a very low accuracy and precision. This result was similar to Niu et al. (2018),
740 confirming the key role of intake variables to provide accurate predictions.

741 ***Limitations and perspectives***

742 In this work, we developed Bayesian linear regressions to assess the risk of reaching
743 target areas, representative of an accuracy around the CH₄ observed, and of
744 exceeding threshold values of CH₄ production. Even if the Bayesian inference is
745 increasingly used in animal science modelling, the development of Bayesian models
746 for this purpose constitutes an originality for the field. A second originality is the
747 assessment of model accuracy and precision using a probabilistic framework. This
748 framework provides a useful information, in addition to the usual evaluation criteria
749 computed in the field, to provide recommendations on which models to use in
750 specific situations. Therefore, the recommended model depends on several criteria,
751 such as the targeted accuracy the modeller fixed, the availability of the variables
752 studied and the interest of using a specific variable representative of a treatment or
753 system under study. Hristov et al. (2018) suggested that the choice of a model has to
754 be determined by the aim for which the model is used (national inventory, assess
755 mitigation strategies, other).

756 Regarding our results, it is important to mention that they are inherently linked to the
757 data we used. The results obtained with RD2 were a better estimation of model
758 accuracy and precision, as this dataset explored records associated with a wider
759 range of CH₄ production. While, RD1 explored only records associated with high CH₄
760 production. Moreover, the comparison conducted in our work is performed in a
761 general framework, as we used a general database representative of several
762 treatment means and regions. The prior distributions over model parameters
763 considered were also representative of a general knowledge, as they were fitted with
764 data from models developed in different contexts. Finally, biases are likely present
765 between the prior distributions fitted and the database used for the Bayesian model
766 development, as some models reported in the empirical model database were

767 developed with data from studies reported in the database of de Ondarza et al.
768 (2023). However, we considered that the impact of these biases was limited due to
769 the high number of models considered to fit the prior distributions. Moreover,
770 removing these studies would have had a negative impact on the amount of data
771 available for developing our models.

772 Our study is also limited by the consideration of only linear models. They are the
773 most widely used in practice due to their simplicity. However, several studies
774 (Appuhamy et al., 2016; Marumo et al., 2023) highlighted that some non-linear
775 models performed better than linear models. In Marumo et al., (2023), the best
776 performing model used DMI, the dietary forage proportion, and a quadratic term of
777 the dietary forage proportion. Moreover, Appuhamy et al. (2016) found that a model
778 representing an exponential relationship between CH₄ production and DMI developed
779 in Mills et al. (2003) performed better than the model representing a linear
780 relationship in European data. Other important explanatory variables such as dietary
781 forage proportion, dietary starch content, acid detergent fiber might also have been
782 considered in our study.

783 Finally, the dietary scenarios considered in our work were studied to illustrate the
784 approach of comparing models by computing their probabilities to reach CH₄
785 production thresholds. This approach could be implemented using reference dietary
786 scenarios (INRAE, USDA, FAO) in the future.

787 **Conclusion**

788 In this work, we assessed the accuracy and precision of CH₄ predictions of ten
789 empirical models by incorporating uncertainty using Bayesian inference. A model
790 using dry matter intake, lipid content and neutral detergent fiber digestibility resulted

791 in the highest accuracy. This model had a high probability to predict at 9% around the
792 CH₄ observed, when exploring a large diversity of diets, and was among the most
793 accurate models, when exploring only high intake level diets. In both cases, its
794 precision was satisfactory. The study highlighted that gross energy intake was more
795 accurate and precise than dry matter intake to predict highly diverse diets, and that
796 milk yield can be an alternative to dry matter intake, as it had a higher or similar
797 accuracy for high intake level diets. The study showed that empirical models that do
798 not use intake or milk production variables had a very low accuracy, highlighting the
799 key role of these variables to predict CH₄. Including dietary composition variables to
800 dry matter intake is recommended for a high-targeted accuracy. Finally, ability of
801 models to predict dietary scenarios was very different depending on the lipid level
802 considered. Our work showed that using the probabilistic framework of Bayesian
803 inference is relevant to recommend models and might help to accurately assess
804 methane dietary mitigation strategies.

805 **Ethics approval**

806 Not applicable.

807 **Data and model availability statement**

808 The supplementary material, script for the Bayesian model development and
809 implementation of accuracy and precision analyses of models, and list of empirical
810 models of enteric CH₄ production used to define the prior distributions are available
811 at Blondiaux (2024).

812 **Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing** 813 **process**

814 During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used Chat GTP in order to improve
815 the English writing. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the
816 content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

817 **Author ORCIDs**

818 Paul Blondiaux: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5878-3974>

819 Edward Hernando Cabezas-Garcia: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7648-904X>

820 Tristan Senga Kiessé: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2710-5825>

821 Rafael Muñoz-Tamayo: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9266-4132>

822 Kristan Foster Reed: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1766-4148>

823 Maguy Eugène: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2111-0597>

824 **Author contributions**

825 Paul Blondiaux: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal Analysis, Investigation,
826 Methodology, Software, Writing – original draft

827 E.H. Cabezas-Garcia: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Supervision,
828 Writing – review & editing

829 Tristan Senga Kiessé: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Methodology,
830 Supervision, Writing – review & editing

831 Rafael Muñoz-Tamayo: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Methodology,
832 Supervision, Writing – review & editing

833 K.F. Reed: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Supervision, Writing –
834 review & editing

835 Maguy Eugène: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology,
836 Project administration, Supervision, Writing – review & editing

837 **Declaration of interest**

838 The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest in relation to the content of
839 the article.

840 **Financial support statement**

841 Paul Blondiaux is funded with a scholarship from the doctoral school ABIES
842 (AgroParisTech, France) and from the INRAE PHASE department (France). This
843 study was conducted as part of a scientific stay of Paul Blondiaux at the department
844 of animal science of Cornell University. This stay was supported by INRAE, the
845 doctoral school ABIES and the graduate school Biosphera of Paris-Saclay University.

846 **Reference**

847 Abril-Pla, O., Andreani, V., Carroll, C., Dong, L., Fonnesbeck, C.J., Kochurov, M., Kumar, R.,
848 Lao, J., Luhmann, C.C., Martin, O.A., Osthege, M., Vieira, R., Wiecki, T., Zinkov, R.,
849 2023. PyMC: a modern, and comprehensive probabilistic programming framework in
850 Python. *PeerJ Comput. Sci.* 9, e1516. <https://doi.org/10.7717/PEERJ-CS.1516/FIG-10>
851 Appuhamy, J.A.D.R.N., France, J., Kebreab, E., 2016. Models for predicting enteric methane
852 emissions from dairy cows in North America, Europe, and Australia and New Zealand.
853 *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 22, 3039–3056. <https://doi.org/10.1111/GCB.13339>
854 Arndt, C., Hristov, A.N., Price, W.J., McClelland, S.C., Pelaez, A.M., Cueva, S.F., Oh, J.,
855 Dijkstra, J., Bannink, A., Bayat, A.R., Crompton, L.A., Eugéne, M.A., Enahoro, D.,
856 Kebreab, E., Kreuzer, M., McGee, M., Martin, C., Newbold, C.J., Reynolds, C.K.,
857 Schwarm, A., Shingfield, K.J., Veneman, J.B., Yáñez-Ruiz, D.R., Yu, Z., 2022. Full
858 adoption of the most effective strategies to mitigate methane emissions by ruminants
859 can help meet the 1.5 °C target by 2030 but not 2050. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.*
860 119. <https://doi.org/10.1073/PNAS.2111294119/-/DCSUPPLEMENTAL>

861 Beauchemin, K.A., Ungerfeld, E.M., Abdalla, A.L., Alvarez, C., Arndt, C., Becquet, P.,
862 Benchaar, C., Berndt, A., Mauricio, R.M., McAllister, T.A., Oyhantçabal, W., Salami,
863 S.A., Shalloo, L., Sun, Y., Tricarico, J., Uwizeye, A., De Camillis, C., Bernoux, M.,
864 Robinson, T., Kebreab, E., 2022. Invited review: Current enteric methane mitigation
865 options. *J. Dairy Sci.* 105, 9297–9326. <https://doi.org/10.3168/JDS.2022-22091>

866 Beauchemin, K.A., Ungerfeld, E.M., Eckard, R.J., Wang, M., 2020. Review: Fifty years of
867 research on rumen methanogenesis: lessons learned and future challenges for
868 mitigation. *Animal* 14, s2–s16. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1751731119003100>

869 Benaouda, M., Martin, C., Li, X., Kebreab, E., Hristov, A.N., Yu, Z., Yáñez-Ruiz, D.R.,
870 Reynolds, C.K., Crompton, L.A., Dijkstra, J., Bannink, A., Schwarm, A., Kreuzer, M.,
871 McGee, M., Lund, P., Hellwing, A.L.F., Weisbjerg, M.R., Moate, P.J., Bayat, A.R.,
872 Shingfield, K.J., Peiren, N., Eugène, M., 2019. Evaluation of the performance of
873 existing mathematical models predicting enteric methane emissions from ruminants:
874 Animal categories and dietary mitigation strategies. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 255,
875 114207. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ANIFEEDSCI.2019.114207>

876 Blake, N.E., Walker, M., Plum, S., Hubbart, J.A., Hatton, J., Mata-Padrino, D., Holásková, I.,
877 Wilson, M.E., 2023. Predicting dry matter intake in beef cattle. *J. Anim. Sci.* 101, 1–12.
878 <https://doi.org/10.1093/JAS/SKAD269>

879 Blondiaux, P., 2024. Evaluation of the precision and accuracy of models of enteric methane
880 emissions from ruminants using Bayesian inference_Code_Supplementary_material -
881 Data INRAE [WWW Document]. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.57745/78UFUC>

882 Brask, M., Lund, P., Hellwing, A.L.F., Poulsen, M., Weisbjerg, M.R., 2013. Enteric methane
883 production, digestibility and rumen fermentation in dairy cows fed different forages with
884 and without rapeseed fat supplementation. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 184, 67–79.
885 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ANIFEEDSCI.2013.06.006>

886 Charmley, E., Williams, S.R.O., Moate B, P.J., Hegarty, R.S., Herd, R.M., Oddy, V.H.,
887 Reyenga, P., Staunton, K.M., Anderson, A., Hannah, M.C., 2016. A universal equation

888 to predict methane production of forage-fed cattle in Australia. *Anim. Prod. Sci.* 56,
889 169–180. <https://doi.org/10.1071/AN15365>

890 Corré, W.J., 2002. Agricultural land use and emissions of methane and nitrous oxide in
891 Europe. *Plant Res. Int.* Wageningen.

892 de Ondarza, M.B., Hristov, A.N., Tricarico, J.M., 2023. A global dataset of enteric methane
893 mitigation experiments with lactating and non-lactating dairy cows conducted from
894 1963 to 2022. *Data Br.* 49, 109459. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.DIB.2023.109459>

895 Delagarde, R., Faverdin, P., Baratte, C., Peyraud, J.L., 2011. Grazeln: a model of herbage
896 intake and milk production for grazing dairy cows. 2. Prediction of intake under
897 rotational and continuously stocked grazing management. *Grass Forage Sci.* 66, 45–
898 60. <https://doi.org/10.1111/J.1365-2494.2010.00770.X>

899 Ellis, J.L., Bannink, A., France, J., Kebreab, E., Dijkstra, J., 2010. Evaluation of enteric
900 methane prediction equations for dairy cows used in whole farm models. *Glob. Chang.*
901 *Biol.* 16, 3246–3256. <https://doi.org/10.1111/J.1365-2486.2010.02188.X>

902 Ellis, J.L., Kebreab, E., Odongo, N.E., McBride, B.W., Okine, E.K., France, J., 2007.
903 Prediction of Methane Production from Dairy and Beef Cattle. *J. Dairy Sci.* 90, 3456–
904 3466. <https://doi.org/10.3168/JDS.2006-675>

905 Feng, X.Y., Dijkstra, J., Bannink, A., van Gastelen, S., France, J., Kebreab, E., 2020.
906 Antimethanogenic effects of nitrate supplementation in cattle: A meta-analysis. *J. Dairy*
907 *Sci.* 103, 11375–11385. <https://doi.org/10.3168/JDS.2020-18541>

908 Gerber, P.-J., Steinfeld, H., Henderson, B., Mottet, A., Opio, C., Dijkman, J., Falcucci, A.,
909 Tempio, G., 2013. Tackling climate change through livestock – A global assessment of
910 emissions and mitigation opportunities. *Food Agric. Organ. United Nations (FAO)*,
911 Rome.

912 Hoffman, M.D., Gelman, A., 2014. The No-U-Turn Sampler: Adaptively Setting Path Lengths
913 in Hamiltonian Monte Carlo. *J. Mach. Learn. Res.* 15, 1593–1623.

914 Hristov, A.N., 2024. Invited review: Advances in nutrition and feed additives to mitigate
915 enteric methane emissions. *J. Dairy Sci.* 107, 4129–4146.
916 <https://doi.org/10.3168/JDS.2023-24440>

917 Hristov, A.N., Kebreab, E., Niu, M., Oh, J., Bannink, A., Bayat, A.R., Boland, T.M., Brito, A.F.,
918 Casper, D.P., Crompton, L.A., Dijkstra, J., Eugène, M., Garnsworthy, P.C., Haque, N.,
919 Hellwing, A.L.F., Huhtanen, P., Kreuzer, M., Kuhla, B., Lund, P., Madsen, J., Martin, C.,
920 Moate, P.J., Muetzel, S., Muñoz, C., Peiren, N., Powell, J.M., Reynolds, C.K.,
921 Schwarm, A., Shingfield, K.J., Storlien, T.M., Weisbjerg, M.R., Yáñez-Ruiz, D.R., Yu,
922 Z., 2018. Symposium review: Uncertainties in enteric methane inventories,
923 measurement techniques, and prediction models. *J. Dairy Sci.* 101, 6655–6674.
924 <https://doi.org/10.3168/JDS.2017-13536>

925 Hristov, A.N., Oh, J., Lee, C., Meinen, R., Montes, F., Ott, T., Firkins, J., Rotz, A., Dell, C.,
926 Adesogan, A., Yang, W., Tricarico, J., Kebreab, E., Waghorn, G., Dijkstra, J., Oosting,
927 S., 2013a. Mitigation of greenhouse gas emissions in livestock production – A review of
928 technical options for non-CO₂ emissions. *FAO Anim. Prod. Heal. Pap. No. 177*. FAO,
929 Rome, Italy.

930 Hristov, A.N., Ott, T., Tricarico, J., Rotz, A., Waghorn, G., Adesogan, A., Dijkstra, J., Montes,
931 F., Oh, J., Kebreab, E., Oosting, S.J., Gerber, P.J., Henderson, B., Makkar, H.P.S.,
932 Firkins, J.L., 2013b. SPECIAL TOPICS — Mitigation of methane and nitrous oxide
933 emissions from animal operations: III. A review of animal management mitigation
934 options. *J. Anim. Sci.* 91, 5095–5113. <https://doi.org/10.2527/JAS.2013-6585>

935 Huhtanen, P., Vanhatalo, A., 1997. Ruminant and total plant cell-wall digestibility estimated by
936 a combined in situ method utilizing mathematical models. *Br. J. Nutr.* 78, 583–598.
937 <https://doi.org/10.1079/BJN19970176>

938 IPCC, 2019. 2019 Refinement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas
939 Inventories.

940 IPCC, 2018. Global Warming of 1.5°C. An IPCC Special Report on the impacts of global
941 warming of 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels and related global greenhouse gas

942 emission pathways, in the context of strengthening the global response to the threat of
943 climate change,. Press.

944 IPCC, 2006. 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories.

945 IPCC, 1997. IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories : Reference Manual.

946 Johnson, K.A., Johnson, D.E., 1995. Methane emissions from cattle. *J. Anim. Sci.* 73, 2483–
947 2492. <https://doi.org/10.2527/1995.7382483X>

948 Knapp, J.R., Laur, G.L., Vadas, P.A., Weiss, W.P., Tricarico, J.M., 2014. Invited review:
949 Enteric methane in dairy cattle production: Quantifying the opportunities and impact of
950 reducing emissions. *J. Dairy Sci.* 97, 3231–3261. <https://doi.org/10.3168/JDS.2013-7234>

951

952 Marumo, J.L., LaPierre, P.A., Van Amburgh, M.E., 2023. Enteric Methane Emissions
953 Prediction in Dairy Cattle and Effects of Monensin on Methane Emissions: A Meta-
954 Analysis. *Animals* 13, 1392. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ANI13081392/S1>

955 Mills, J.A.N., Kebreab, E., Yates, C.M., Crompton, L.A., Cammell, S.B., Dhanoa, M.S.,
956 Agnew, R.E., France, J., 2003. Alternative approaches to predicting methane
957 emissions from dairy cows. *J. Anim. Sci.* 81, 3141–3150.

958 Moe, P.W., Tyrrell, H.F., 1979. Methane Production in Dairy Cows. *J. Dairy Sci.* 62, 1583–
959 1586. [https://doi.org/10.3168/JDS.S0022-0302\(79\)83465-7](https://doi.org/10.3168/JDS.S0022-0302(79)83465-7)

960 Moraes, L.E., Strathe, A.B., Fadel, J.G., Casper, D.P., Kebreab, E., 2014. Prediction of
961 enteric methane emissions from cattle. *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 20, 2140–2148.
962 <https://doi.org/10.1111/GCB.12471>

963 Muñoz-Tamayo, R., Nielsen, B.L., Gagaoua, M., Gondret, F., Krause, E.T., Morgavi, D.P.,
964 Olsson, I.A.S., Pastell, M., Taghipoor, M., Tedeschi, L., Veissier, I., Nawroth, C., 2022.
965 Seven steps to enhance Open Science practices in animal science. *PNAS Nexus* 1.
966 <https://doi.org/10.1093/PNASNEXUS/PGAC106>

967 Myhre, G., Shindell, D., Bréon, F.-M., Collins, W., Fuglestedt, J., Huang, J., Koch, D.,
968 Lamarque, J.-F., Lee, D., Mendoza, B., Nakajima, T., Robock, A., Stephens, G.,
969 Takemura, T., Zhang, H., 2013. Anthropogenic and Natural Radiative Forcing. *Clim.*

970 Chang. 2013 Phys. Sci. Basis. Contrib. Work. Gr. I to Fifth Assess. Rep. Intergov.
971 Panel Clim. Chang. [Stocker, T.F., D. Qin, G.-K. Plattner, M. Tignor, S.K. Allen, J.
972 Boschung, A. Nauels, Y. Xia, 659–740.
973 <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107415324.018>

974 Nielsen, N.I., Volden, H., Åkerlind, M., Brask, M., Hellwing, A.L.F., Storlien, T., Bertilsson, J.,
975 2013. A prediction equation for enteric methane emission from dairy cows for use in
976 NorFor. Acta Agric. Scand. Sect. A - Anim. Sci. 63, 126–130.
977 <https://doi.org/10.1080/09064702.2013.851275>

978 Niu, M., Kebreab, E., Hristov, A.N., Oh, J., Arndt, C., Bannink, A., Bayat, A.R., Brito, A.F.,
979 Boland, T., Casper, D., Crompton, L.A., Dijkstra, J., Eugène, M.A., Garnsworthy, P.C.,
980 Haque, M.N., Hellwing, A.L.F., Huhtanen, P., Kreuzer, M., Kuhla, B., Lund, P., Madsen,
981 J., Martin, C., McClelland, S.C., McGee, M., Moate, P.J., Muetzel, S., Muñoz, C.,
982 O’Kiely, P., Peiren, N., Reynolds, C.K., Schwarm, A., Shingfield, K.J., Storlien, T.M.,
983 Weisbjerg, M.R., Yáñez-Ruiz, D.R., Yu, Z., 2018. Prediction of enteric methane
984 production, yield, and intensity in dairy cattle using an intercontinental database. Glob.
985 Chang. Biol. 24, 3368–3389. <https://doi.org/10.1111/GCB.14094>

986 Ramin, M., Huhtanen, P., 2013. Development of equations for predicting methane emissions
987 from ruminants. J. Dairy Sci. 96, 2476–2493. <https://doi.org/10.3168/JDS.2012-6095>

988 Reed, K.F., Arhonditsis, G.B., France, J., Kebreab, E., 2016. Technical note: Bayesian
989 calibration of dynamic ruminant nutrition models. J. Dairy Sci. 99, 6362–6370.
990 <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2015-10708>

991 Reynolds, C.K., Crompton, L.A., Mills, J.A.N., 2011. Improving the efficiency of energy
992 utilisation in cattle. Anim. Prod. Sci. 51, 6–12. <https://doi.org/10.1071/AN10160>

993 Santiago-Juarez, B., Moraes, L.E., Appuhamy, J.A.D.R.N., Pellikaan, W.F., Casper, D.P.,
994 Tricarico, J., Kebreab, E., 2016. Prediction and evaluation of enteric methane
995 emissions from lactating dairy cows using different levels of covariate information.
996 Anim. Prod. Sci. 56, 557–564. <https://doi.org/10.1071/AN15496>

997 Storlien, T.M., Volden, H., Almøy, T., Beauchemin, K.A., McAllister, T.A., Harstad, O.M.,
998 2014. Prediction of enteric methane production from dairy cows. *Acta Agric. Scand.*
999 *Sect. A — Anim. Sci.* 64, 98–109. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09064702.2014.959553>

1000 Tedeschi, L.O., Abdalla, A.L., Álvarez, C., Anuga, S.W., Arango, J., Beauchemin, K.A.,
1001 Becquet, P., Berndt, A., Burns, R., De Camillis, C., Chará, J., Echazarreta, J.M.,
1002 Hassouna, Mc.D. sign@lynd., Kenny, D., Mathot, M., Mauricio, R.M., McClelland, S.C.,
1003 Niu, M., Onyango, A.A., Parajuli, R., Pereira, L.G.R., Del Prado, A., Paz Tieri, M.,
1004 Uwizeye, A., Kebreab, E., 2022. Quantification of methane emitted by ruminants: a
1005 review of methods. *J. Anim. Sci.* 100, 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1093/JAS/SKAC197>

1006 Tyrrell, H.F., Reid, J.T., 1965. Prediction of the energy value of cow's milk. *J. Dairy Sci.* 48,
1007 1215–1223. [https://doi.org/10.3168/JDS.S0022-0302\(65\)88430-2](https://doi.org/10.3168/JDS.S0022-0302(65)88430-2)

1008 Ungerfeld, E.M., 2020. Metabolic Hydrogen Flows in Rumen Fermentation: Principles and
1009 Possibilities of Interventions. *Front. Microbiol.* 11, 528227.
1010 <https://doi.org/10.3389/FMICB.2020.00589/BIBTEX>

1011 van Lingen, H.J., Fadel, J.G., Moraes, L.E., Bannink, A., Dijkstra, J., 2019. Bayesian
1012 mechanistic modeling of thermodynamically controlled volatile fatty acid, hydrogen and
1013 methane production in the bovine rumen. *J. Theor. Biol.* 480.
1014 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtbi.2019.08.008>

1015 Warner, D., Hatew, B., Podesta, S.C., Klop, G., Van Gastelen, S., Van Laar, H., Dijkstra, J.,
1016 Bannink, A., 2016. Effects of nitrogen fertilisation rate and maturity of grass silage on
1017 methane emission by lactating dairy cows. *Animal* 10, 34–43.
1018 <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1751731115001640>

1019 Zheng, H., Wang, H., Yan, T., 2017. Modelling enteric methane emissions from milking dairy
1020 cows with Bayesian networks. *Proc. - 2016 IEEE Int. Conf. Bioinforma. Biomed. BIBM*
1021 2016 1635–1640. <https://doi.org/10.1109/BIBM.2016.7822764>

1022